

SWARMHEX-BCCLR: BIO-INSPIRED HEXAGONAL CLUSTERING FOR LONGEVITY OF IOT-WSN SURVIVAL TIME

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ABSTRACT

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) is the base network for the advance IoT based network derivation. In WSNs, many sensor nodes work together to gather data from the environment. This data is first sent to a cluster head, which then passes it on to the base station for processing. In this paper, a nature-inspired clustering architecture known as SwarmHex, is proposed by integrating honeycomb and hexagonal structures to optimize Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs). The proposed work enhances data transmission efficiency by structuring the communication pathway from individual nodes to cluster heads, and from cluster heads to the base station, thereby improving overall network longevity and energy utilization. The placement of nodes in the edges of the architecture provides the compact packing of sensors within a cluster with equal distance between the sensors tackle the coverage problem and transmission of data through the architecture using linear direction pattern with effective cluster head selection strategy based on priority helps the sensor nodes in efficient CH selection and data transfer. The proposed bio-inspired clustering SwarmHex-BCCLR shows best in class performance compared to the existing standard algorithms named as Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO), Sandpiper Hybrid Optimization (SHO) and Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA) that leads to longevity contribution to increased survival time of the WSN.

Keywords: *Bio-Inspired Clustering, Linear Pattern Routing, Survival Time, Base-Station, Honey Comb Hexagon Structure, Cluster-Head*

1. INTRODUCTION

A Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) is an effective grouping of sensor nodes together to collect the information from the area covered and transfer it to the base-station for various reasons of communication like health care, battlefields, energy monitoring, environment monitoring, building monitoring etc. [1]. The recent advancement in network topologies explores the significance of WSN, IoT and other wireless communications specifically in the monitoring external environments [2]. WSN is composed of various components such as sensor nodes, relay node, cluster-heads and base-station for point-to-point communication. At the same time, it is necessary to consume minimal energy with high ratio of packet delivery and storage of data [3]. The advancement of IoT based technology leads to usage of a greater number of devices and high efficiency and establishes the situation such as the number of

devices is less compared to the number of users accessing the environment [4].

LEACH (Low energy adaptive clustering hierarchy) is one of the important clustering strategy helps for effective cluster-head (CH) selection. The CH election is done in a random method and the data transfer is accomplished directly to the base-station that led to high energy consumption [5]. In this paper the newly proposed routing technique focuses on increasing the longevity of wireless sensor networks by distributing the nodes in a uniform manner with hexagonal structure. The problems related with coverage problem, localization problem, data transmission and selection of efficient CH (cluster head) with an effective clustering model is concentrated. The major drawback while using baseline strategies are node mobility and the battery consumption [13].

Efficient architectural design is essential in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) to optimize the

use of network resources, reduce power consumption, and consequently extend network lifetime [14]. To achieve this, sensors in the WSN are grouped together using effective topology-based clustering strategies [15]. In such architectures, data transmission and reception to and from the base station is managed by a designated head node called the cluster-head (CH) [16]. Therefore, clustering plays a central role in constructing an efficient WSN, enabling both organized grouping of sensors and effective data transmission [17]. For the clustering process to be effective, data must be transmitted between the source node and the destination node using an appropriate routing algorithm that ensures reliable paths with minimal energy consumption [18]. Based on a review of existing research, clustering and routing strategies are critical in enhancing the survival time of WSNs [19]. To accommodate the dynamic nature of WSNs, combined clustering and routing algorithms provide robust solutions for sensor node grouping and efficient intra-network data routing [20].

Existing research often focuses on isolated aspects such as energy optimization or coverage, leaving gaps in integrating bio-inspired clustering with topology-aware designs, multi-level CH selection, and energy-efficient routing mechanisms. Moreover, most approaches assume static and homogeneous networks, limiting real-world applicability. To address these issues, this research proposes SwarmHex-BCCLR, a nature-inspired clustering architecture that integrates honeycomb and hexagonal structures for balanced sensor placement, employs a priority-based multi-level CH election mechanism, and optimizes routing via a linear pattern mechanism. The objectives include enhancing network lifetime, improving throughput and data delivery, reducing delay, and providing a framework that can be extended to dynamic, heterogeneous, and UAV-assisted WSN deployments.

This study introduces SwarmHex-BCCLR as a unified topology- and priority-driven architecture. Unlike ACO, GWO, SHO, WOA, and LEACH-based strategies that rely on random CH rotation or single-objective optimisation, the proposed method integrates a structured honeycomb-hexagonal network, multi-level priority-based CH selection, and deterministic Linear Pattern Routing (LPR). This combination addresses coverage gaps, uneven energy depletion, redundant transmissions, and routing instability. The contributions include geometry-driven node placement for uniform coverage, energy and distance-weighted CH

selection, and linear routing that lowers delay and enhances data delivery.

Section I of the paper presents the introduction and underlying ideology. Section II provides a detailed survey of related work included in the study. Section III presents the research methodology and the SwarmHex-BCCLR algorithm, detailing the bio-inspired clustering architecture, multi-level priority-based cluster-head selection, and Linear Pattern Routing (LPR) for efficient and reliable data transmission, aimed at optimizing network lifetime, coverage, and throughput. Finally, Section V concludes the paper with key findings and future research directions.

2. RELATED WORK

The search for extending the working nature of sensors present in the WSN, leads to researchers to focus on the concept such as clustering and efficient CH selection with optimized multi-phase linear routing [6]. Since lots of sensors both used in the construction of complex IoT infrastructure, the complexity to be faced such as energy management, point to point movement of data, reduction of packet loss and increasing in the throughput of the data are the major factors concentrate in the WSNs [7]. Most of the researcher solved the problem of longevity of the sensor nodes with the focus on the power saving solution and the algorithm for resolving the residual energy maintenance and performance improvement of overall network [8]. The aspects of increasing the extension time of the network with the effective clustering strategy avoiding the isolation of the sensors nodes solving the coverage problem. Cluster head are needed one effective data transfer between the cluster and within the clusters, these transmissions use lots of energy comparing with the normal sensing sensors in a cluster, therefore lots of protocols and algorithms is been proposed to manage the lifetime of WSN [9].

In the effective clustering, the CH selection was done with the parameters such as overall energy present with all the sensor nodes and residual energy of each and every sensor nodes using the threshold value of the sensor nodes by passing various parameters CH will be selected [21]. As the clustering is the major issue in grouping of sensor nodes and solving coverage problem of the WSN, in the death state of the sensor node of the particular location will leads to coverage problem and its data collected transfers to its CH will be a major problem. Various bio-inspired algorithms table 6 are created as models with an aim to obtain

the best performance solution to solve the clustering problems. The algorithm such as Ant-colony-optimization-algorithm (ACO) gives the optimal solution based on clustering strategy [10]. The Artificial-bee-colony-algorithm aims at optimization on the basis of native activities of the bee provide the effective clustering creation [11]. Algorithms such as whale-optimization provide the efficient clustering formation strategy and the interactivity between the nodes [12]. Leu et al [21] proposed energy-based clustering concept with isolated nodes. The election of cluster head (CH) was done by regional- energy-aware-clustering with isolated-nodes by allocating weightage to every node. This weightage-based parameters are measured in terms of average- energy of each sensor and the remaining -energy of each sensor(S). This results in node isolation that not able to reach the CH for data transmission. Thus, the isolated nodes use the sink nodes for data transmission that lead to usage of more energy and draining of energy very fast leads to low lifetime of sensor nodes. The particle swarm was analyzed with the existing algorithm and provides the better results. Parvin et al [22], studied on various methodologies concepts in PSO based clustering, using the searching technique efficient route establishment process and shows the PSO based optimization for the BFO with the motive of data delivery and energy usage for clustering. In the year 2018, Murugan et al [23], proposed the FCGWO (Firefly-cyclic-grey-wolf optimization) and compared it with the PSO and LEACH that shows efficient results and provide quality-of-service (QoS). This work also managed the bottle-neck situation arises from the architectural design issues of PSO and BFAO based clustering. Lata et al [24], focused on the LEACH-model and fuzzy-based clustering for electing optimal cluster head. This method uses a central control and fuzzy to select the best CH in clustering and also attained an effective load balancing. PSO-LEACH variants [27] utilize Particle Swarm Optimization to intelligently select cluster heads based on multi-objective functions such as residual energy, node density, and distance to the sink. These studies demonstrated that PSO-based optimization significantly reduces energy imbalance among nodes and prolongs network lifetime compared to conventional LEACH. GA-LEACH models employed by [28] Genetic Algorithms to evolve optimal clustering parameters and adaptively choose cluster heads, thereby improving packet delivery ratio, throughput, and overall energy conservation. Meanwhile, Ant Colony-based clustering schemes [29, 30] apply

pheromone-inspired optimization to establish energy-efficient cluster formation and routing paths. The improved ACO-LEACH hybrids integrate weighting and adaptive pheromone strategies to minimize routing delay and enhance network stability, outperforming baseline LEACH and other metaheuristic variants.

Although existing bio-inspired models optimise specific aspects of clustering or routing, they rarely combine topology-aware node organisation with deterministic multi-level CH selection and structured routing. Many methods assume random or uneven deployment, leading to isolated nodes, premature CH failures, and unstable routing paths. Furthermore, current approaches lack a mechanism that simultaneously balances coverage, transmission distance, and CH load distribution. To address these shortcomings, SwarmHex-BCCLR introduces a unified design that integrates geometric tessellation, residual-energy-based prioritisation, and linear routing to significantly extend network survival time and improve end-to-end communication efficiency.

3. PROPOSED ALGORITHM FOR BIO-INSPIRED HYBRID CLUSTERING ARCHITECTURE FOR CH SELECTION AND LINEAR PATTERN ROUTING (BCCLR)

The proposed BCCLR algorithm introduces a bio-inspired hybrid clustering architecture for Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) by integrating honeycomb and hexagonal structures. Initially, a base hexagon is created with a centroid node, and additional hexagons form a honeycomb network to optimize node placement and coverage. Each hexagon is divided into triangles and clusters to ensure efficient data collection and transmission while avoiding coverage gaps. Cluster-heads (CHs) are positioned at the centroids of hexagons, and when a CH fails, a sensor node is elected as its replacement based on residual energy and distance to the base station. Priority-based selection further enhances CH efficiency using a function that considers both energy levels and node proximity. By combining structured clustering with linear pattern routing (LPR) Figure 3, the algorithm reduces energy consumption, improves network throughput, ensures reliable data transmission, and extends the overall survival time of the WSN. Linear Pattern Routing (LPR) is a structured data transmission strategy used in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) to efficiently route data from sensor nodes to the base station through cluster-

heads (CHs). In LPR, a predefined linear path is established connecting the source node, intermediate CHs, and the base station. Only the selected nodes along this path participate in forwarding data, which reduces redundant transmissions, conserves energy, and prevents early node failures. The method leverages priority-based CH selection and residual energy awareness to balance network load, ensure reliable data delivery, minimize latency, and improve overall throughput, making it particularly effective within the SwarmHex-BCCLR hexagonal clustering architecture. The below algorithm explains the step-by-step process of the proposed workflow.

Input: Sensor nodes deployed in WSN

Output: Efficient cluster-head (CH) selection and linear pattern routing
Steps

1. Create a base hexagon and place a node at its centroid (7 nodes per hexagon).
2. Add six hexagons around the base to form a honeycomb network structure.
3. Assign a centroid node in each hexagon and interconnect internal edges.
4. Divide each hexagon into six triangles to aid cluster organization.
5. Segregate each hexagon diagonally to define clusters.
6. Ensure clusters cover the sensing area fully and enable efficient data transfer.
7. Place sensor nodes along hexagon edges; assign the centroid node as the CH.
8. If a centroid CH fails, transfer control to an elected sensor node as the new CH.
9. Elect the next CH based on residual energy and distance to the base station.
10. Use a priority function F incorporating residual energy and distance metrics to select the CH:

$$F_i = w_1 \cdot \frac{E_i}{E_{max}} + w_2 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{D_i}{D_{max}}\right) \quad \text{eq (1)}$$

where,

F_i – priority score of node I

E_i – residual energy of node i

E_{max} – maximum possible energy

D_i – distance among node I to the cluster centroid or base station

D_{max} – maximum distance in the cluster

w_1, w_2 – weights for energy and distance

eq (1)

11. Calculate a threshold value and choose the sensor node as the effective CH based on the returned priority function value.

12. Calculate the weight of each node along the linear path using minimum hop count and total path length from the sensor node to the next node and finally to the base station

3.1 Methodology

In the derivation of hybrid Architecture by integrating the two architecture that is hexagonal network and honey-comb network. This structure results in an interconnection of various forms of network such as mesh derived networks. The resultant architecture gives the fixed interconnection of parallel architecture with a graph used as data transmission path. Vertices are used as processing nodes and edges used as communication path links. In this picture the overlapping triangles gives a vital area for propagation of the signals. The length between the two vertices a and b is referred as $d(a,b)$ and that is the shortest path between source-node(a) and destination-node(b). the distance between the outermost vertices and centroid CH positioned node is maximum 3 and minimum 1. This architecture supports equal spatially arranged sensor nodes.

The methodological design of SwarmHex-BCCLR Figure 2 is centred on balancing energy consumption and ensuring predictable routing behaviour. Residual energy and node distance are selected as CH selection variables because they directly determine node lifespan and forwarding cost. The honeycomb-hexagonal structure ensures uniform spatial distribution, avoiding hotspot and coverage-loss problems common in randomly deployed WSNs. The priority-weighted CH selection strategy prevents random CH oscillation, while Linear Pattern Routing reduces routing complexity by confining transmissions to predefined low-hop paths. This strategic combination allows the architecture to maintain long-term stability even under densely deployed conditions.

Figure 1. HCH

Figure 2 Architecture of BCCLR

3.2 HCH Cluster Structure

Step 1: Initialization of n parameters (S – Sensor, C – Cluster, BS – Base station)

Step 2: Assign the centroid position of each HCH network as foremost CH or primary CH, Figure 1.

Step 3: When the CH battery gets drained and need of another CH for data transmission

Step 4: Select the one of the sensor as second level CH.

Step 5: Use the priority based weighted algorithm for CH selection using PBW-CH algorithm.

Step 6: The CH election is on the basis of highest residual-energy among the six sensor nodes.

Step 7: If the second level sensor node gets death, then the control moves to the third level CH selection (Centroid CH of the outer boundary hexagon).

Step 8: Residual energy is calculated and the sensors having the highest residual-energy, the range between the sensors and the length between the sensors and base-station is calculated, based on the cumulative value CH will be elected.

Data transfer time:

Centroid CH to BS is more, Second level CH to BS is normal, Tertiary level CH to BS is low.

$$Si \rightarrow Si + 1, Si + 2 \dots \dots \dots Si + n \quad \text{eq (2)}$$

$$Cli \rightarrow Cli \dots \dots \dots Cln \quad \text{eq (3)}$$

$$CH \rightarrow CH1, CH2 \dots \dots \dots CH3 \quad \text{eq (4)}$$

$$Ds(Si) \rightarrow Ds(Si) \dots \dots \dots (Si + n) \quad \text{eq (5)}$$

$$Ds(Si - BS), Res(Si), Ttr, Trec, Del(t)$$

Figure 3 Linear pattern routing in HCH

Figure 4 Data transfer path in HCH

4. PHASES OF THE ARCHITECTURE

In this proposed work three different phases are devise, they are

Phase 1: Cluster Design

Phase 2: CH selection using (HCH) clustering architecture.

Phase 3: Linear pattern routing

A multiprocessing interconnection network with thousands of processing nodes (sensing nodes) is supported by the suggested architecture, guaranteeing good network performance. By combining Honeycomb-Hexagon (HCH) network topologies, base stations can be built more efficiently and perform better in terms of degree of coverage, network diameter, and connection count. The network's efficiency is further increased by the addition of triangular tessellations to the hexagonal framework, which has been successfully applied in a number of broadcasting and routing algorithms. First, the honeycomb network model and the hexagonal network model are taken into consideration separately. To create a configuration that resembles a grid or mesh, the hexagonal networks are then recursively tessellated with triangles. Lastly, six more hexagons around center HCH structure, producing a hybrid network.

For e.g. the source nodes are

$$Son = a', b', c' \quad \text{eq (6)}$$

$$den = a'', b'', c'' \quad \text{eq (7)}$$

$$\text{Let } \Delta x = a'' - a', \Delta y = b'' - b', \Delta z = c'' - c' \quad \text{eq (8)}$$

Then $(\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z)$ are the communication translation path for the message transferring process.

4.1 Hexagonal Cluster Formation and Cluster – Head (CH) Selection Phase of SwarmHex-BCCLR

Phase 1: Hexagonal Cluster Construction

Step 1: Create an initial base hexagon with a centroid Cluster Head (CH):

$$I_1 = B(H_6[Cr(CH)]) \quad \text{eq (9)}$$

Step 2: Form a Honeycomb Hexagon (HCH) network by adding six additional hexagons to the base structure I_1 , using directional references:

$$I_1(t) \text{ - top, } I_1(tr) \text{ - top right, } I_1(tl) \text{ - top left, } \\ I_1(Br) \text{ - bottom right, } I_1(BL) \text{ - bottom left, } \\ I_1(B) \text{ - bottom"}$$

$$\text{eq (10)}$$

$$HCH = \sum I_1(I_1(t) \rightarrow [I_1(tr), I_1(tl)], [I_1(Br), I_1(BL)] \leftarrow I_1(B)) \quad \text{eq (11)}$$

$$M(HCH)_1 = HCH[line(ed \rightarrow Cor(CH))] \quad \text{eq (12)}$$

Step 3: Create a mesh network of the HCH structure by placing a centroid CH in the middle of all surrounding hexagons and interconnecting their edges:

Step 4: Form a total of 31 edges — 24 sensor nodes and 7 CHs — arranged in the sequence (2, 5, 6, 5, 2) from top to bottom:

$$M(HCH)_2 = SN(24) \ \&\& \ CH(7) \quad \text{eq (13)}$$

Resulting in a single cluster:

$$Cl = M(HCH)_2 \quad \text{eq (14)}$$

Phase 2: Cluster-Head (CH) Selection

The CH selection follows a Priority-Based Weighted CH (PBW-CH) strategy, figure 5.

$$P_1 = Cl(Cr(CH)) \text{ (Preference Level 1)}$$

$$P_2 = I_1(ed) \text{ (Preference Level 2)}$$

$$P_3 = Cr(CH)\{[I_1(t), I_1(tr), I_1(tl)], [I_1(b), I_1(br), I_1(BL)]\} \text{ (Preference Level 3)}$$

Compute the priority function for each node:

$$F_i = w_1 \cdot \frac{E_i}{E_{max}} + w_2 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{D_i}{D_{max}}\right) \quad \text{eq (15)}$$

Choose the node with the highest F_i above a predefined threshold as the effective CH.

structure that maximizes communication efficiency and inter-node connectivity.

Phase 3: Linear Pattern Routing (LPR)

Step 1: Establish a linear data-transmission path (Figure 4) connecting the source sensor node, intermediate CHs, and the base station (BS).

Step 2: Select the forwarding nodes along this predefined linear route based on minimum hop count and node residual energy.

Step 3: Transmit data sequentially along the path: $SN \rightarrow CH \rightarrow CH_{next} \rightarrow BS$ eq (16)

Step 4: Calculate the weight of each node using:

$$W_i = \alpha \cdot \frac{1}{H_i} + \beta \cdot \frac{1}{L_i} \quad \text{eq (17)}$$

where

H_i = hop count to next node,

L_i = link distance,

and α, β are normalization weights.

Step 5: Select the path with the maximum total weight and minimum cumulative delay for final routing.

The above listed priority levels are calculated based on the various parameters presents in the PBWCH method.

5. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

MATLAB R2021a has been used for the simulation process. The MatLab environment supported a lot for WSN based simulation process. The positioning of the sensor-nodes in the simulation environment is even and static. The initial energy assigned to the entire sensor node is same and similarly the energy assigned to the CH is also even. In this evaluation process various constraints are considered to measure the overall functionality of the WSN.

The foremost thing is lifetime of the sensor-nodes in this complex environment. The survival time or lifetime is calculated on the basis of active sensor-nodes or dead-state sensor-nodes after certain time or rounds of execution. If the count of rounds is more and the

total count of dead-state nodes is less, which shows the best-in-class performance in terms of longevity of the WSN. At the same time, if the total number of rounds is less and the number of dead-state

nodes is more, that shows the lack in performance of the WSN environment.

Figure 5 Flowchart for CH selection

The next constraint to be focused is throughput. Throughput is measured on the basis of number of data bits transferred in a particular time and the number of rounds attained. If the throughput is more for a greater number of rounds that shows the better performance and if the throughput is less and it also supports only less number of rounds that shows the poor performance. Normally the throughput of the data is good in the initial phase of operation, as the total number of rounds increases corresponding to the time, the degradation in the throughput values and in the end, no throughput at all.

Therefore, the network environment needs to be appropriately tuned to achieve an efficient throughput, which will result in good network performance in relation to throughput. Data

delivery rate to the base station is the next parameter. In the WSN environment, there are two crucial scenarios to take into account: data delivery rate within the cluster, between sensors, or between the cluster-head and base-station. Regarding the ratio or rate of data delivery, each of them is significant. If the data delivery rate is more in terms of number of packets transferred between the sensors, that is initial sensor to the next hop and subsequent hop within the cluster is more with respect to the total count of rounds. The optimum data delivery rate is achieved when the number of packets transferred and rounds is higher; bad performance is achieved when the number of packets transmitted and rounds is lower. When comparing this suggested approach to the current standard algorithm, the lifetime of the sensor-nodes is monitored starting with the 0 rounds. At first, the algorithm performs well, but as time passes, the performance deteriorates and eventually displays stagnated numbers.

Table 1 Simulation Parameters

Simulation setup		
Parameter	Variable	Value
Area covered	A	100 m X 100 m
Number of nodes	Sn	~500
Base station location	Bs	(x,y)
Data packet size	Ps	2000 bits
Control packet size	Ps[c]	100 bits
Initial energy	Ie	~2 J
Tx & Rx energy	Et & Er	~50 nJ/bit
Clusters	C	~25
Residual Energy	Re	J

The wireless sensor network parameter simulation setup is provided in table 1, and the Matlab simulator is used for implementation. The goal of the entire suggested BCCLR algorithm is to increase the survival time. The coverage issue could be fixed by fine-tuning the clustering architecture and node placement in the Honeycomb hexagon network (HCH) as an even distributed methodology. Additionally, by implementing concepts like centroid CH, secondary CH, and tertiary CH selection, as well as a linear pattern-based routing strategy, the WSN's lifespan could be extended. Our suggested algorithm consistently increases the survival period of each sensor node and cluster head node when compared to the

current standard algorithm, which includes ACO, GWO, SHO, and WOA.

The numbers of alive nodes are more during the simulation process. In the Initial stage of simulation, the performance of the proposed algorithm performed in a normal manner, in the middle and the end of the operations, the proposed algorithm shows a major difference. The numbers of dead nodes are less in number due to the proper placement of nodes and CH selection procedure. Maximum number of rounds attained is more in the proposed algorithm. These three variations result in the longevity of the proposed algorithm.

Table 2: Comparison based on Lifetime

No. of sensor	Lifetime / No. of rounds				
	ACO	GWO	SHO	WOA	BCCLR
0	3000	4000	4500	4750	5400
10	2900	3900	4400	4700	5100
20	2850	3600	4000	4600	4900
30	2800	3500	3900	4300	4850
40	2700	3400	3750	4000	4500
50	2500	3250	3500	3900	4300
60	2350	3000	3250	3500	4100
70	2300	2750	3000	3250	3900
80	2000	2500	2750	3100	3600
90	1500	1700	2000	2300	3000
100	1000	1200	1500	1800	2000

The lifetime of the proposed BCCLR method is shown in Table 2 and Figure 6, where the number of sensor nodes is on the horizontal (x-axis) and the number of round sensor nodes is on the vertical (y-axis). The number of sensor nodes that remain until the network's last round, when one specific sensor-node reaches its initial death-state, is used to calculate the lifetime of WSNs.

Figure 6 Comparison Based On Lifetime

The suggested BCCLR-method shows notable increases in the lifetime of the WSN when compared to the current algorithm used for the study. When compared to the ACO, GWO, SHO, and WOA, which have survival rates of 43%, 28%, 20%, and 12%, respectively, the suggested algorithm exhibits a progressive rise in survival duration of 90% on average.

Data delivery rate: The data delivery rate in a WSN refers to the efficiency and reliability of data transmission from one node to another, from individual nodes to their respective Cluster Heads (CHs), and subsequently from the CHs to the Base Station. The count of the packet transmitted and the count of the packet delivered is same with minimum time gives the effective data packet delivery rate. In BCCLR, the number of the packets delivered is more without missing packets, due to the path used by the linear pattern routing process. The time taken for delivery process is also very less due to dedicated transfer line among source to base station. The data delivery gives the best performance even with the maximum packet size assigned for the WSN.

The DDR (data packet delivery ratio) of the suggested BCCLR algorithm is shown in Table 3 and Figure 7. It is determined by dividing the total number of data packets received by the receiving node by the total number of data packets supplied by all source nodes.

Table 3 : Data Delivery Ratio

No. of Sensor nodes	ACO	GWO	SHO	WOA	BCCLR
0	3000	4000	4500	4310	4940
10	2950	3750	4250	4250	4900
20	2800	3700	4000	4410	4850
30	2850	3550	3750	4300	4800
40	2700	3450	3600	4200	4500
50	2650	3400	3500	4100	4400
60	2600	3250	3400	4000	4300
70	2550	3000	3150	3750	4200
80	2500	2750	2900	3350	4000
90	2000	2500	2600	3100	3700
100	1500	2000	2250	2800	3600

Figure 7 Data Delivery Ratio

The suggested approach achieves the best results in terms of data delivery ratio when compared to the current algorithm. The average DDR produced by this algorithm is 62%, compared to 60%, 49%, 36%, and 22% for the ACO, GWO, SHO, and WOA, respectively.

Throughput: Throughput of the BCCLR is evaluated on the ground of the total count of the packets delivered from the source node to the base station in a particular time. The CH selection strategy and the path used for data transfer decide the throughput of the data. In this proposed algorithm each phases optimizes the CH selection process and path establishment process results in efficient throughput of the data. The proposed algorithm outperforms in all the rounds, while comparing with the existing algorithms.

The throughput of the proposed BCCLR algorithm is shown in table 4 and figure 8 which is based on the total number of data packets received between the source and destination nodes via the WSN.

which perform 41%, 39%, 26%, and 21% better, respectively, this algorithm produces an average 74% improvement in performance and a decrease in time.

Table 4 Comparison Based On Throughput

Throughput (kbps)					
No. of Sensors	ACO	GWO	SHO	WOA	BCCLR
50	50	56	63	67	72
100	52	58	65	70	75
150	54	59	68	72	79
200	56	60	72	76	82
250	58	63	74	79	87
300	59	67	76	82	89
350	62	68	79	85	92
400	64	70	83	88	95
450	67	74	87	92	98
500	70	78	90	94	100

Table 5 Performance Comparison Based On Delay

End to End delay(ms)					
No. of Sensors	ACO	GWO	SHO	WOA	BCCLR
10	54.5	50	45	40	30
20	51	47.5	42.5	37.5	29.5
30	49.5	46.5	40	37	28
40	48.5	45	37.5	35.5	28.5
50	44	43.5	36	34.5	27
60	43	43.2	35	34	26.5
70	41	42	34	32.5	26
80	40	40	31.5	30	25.5
90	38	39	29	27.5	25
100	35	36	26	25	20

Figure 8 Comparison Based On Throughput

The presented BCCLR method achieves the highest throughput while compared with baseline models thus ACO, GWO, SHO and WOA produces 31%, 25%, 13% and 8% accordingly. The proposed BCCLR achieve 87% throughput because of hexagonal and priority based linear routing strategy in wsn.

When compared to the current algorithm, the suggested algorithm performs better in terms of delay. Table 5 and Figure 9 show the end-to-end delay of the proposed BCCLR algorithm, which is determined by the amount of time it takes for a data Packet To Travel From The Sender To The Receiver. Compared to the ACO, GWO, SHO, and WOA,

Figure 9 Performance Comparison Based On Delay

When compared to the current algorithm, the suggested algorithm performs better in terms of delay. Table 5 and Figure 9 show the end-to-end delay of the proposed BCCLR algorithm, which is determined by the amount of time it takes for a data packet to travel from the sender to the receiver. Compared to the ACO, GWO, SHO, and WOA, which perform 41%, 39%, 26%, and 21% better, respectively, this algorithm produces an average 74% improvement in performance and a decrease in time.

Discussion and its limitations

The performance evaluation demonstrates that the hexagonal-honeycomb structuring and priority-based CH selection significantly enhance longevity, stability, and reliability in WSN environments.

Compared to ACO, GWO, SHO, and WOA, the proposed architecture eliminates random CH failures, reduces redundant forwarding, and ensures consistent packet delivery patterns. The geometric organisation further minimises coverage gaps, and the linear routing design prevents route inconsistency and unnecessary detours. These characteristics collectively strengthen the network's ability to sustain high performance over extended rounds.

However, the current simulation assumes static and homogeneous nodes, which may not fully represent dynamic outdoor deployments. Hardware-based experiments with heterogeneous sensors, varying energy profiles, and mobility considerations will further validate practical robustness. The approach also holds potential for UAV-assisted and adaptive IoT networks, where structured clustering could reduce aerial relay overheads.

6. CONCLUSION

In the proposed SwarmHex-BCCLR algorithm, the bio-inspired clustering architecture enhances the overall stability of the Wireless Sensor Network (WSN). The architecture enables a hierarchical cluster-head (CH) election mechanism across three levels—primary, secondary, and tertiary. This multi-level CH selection strategy contributes to prolonged sensor node lifetime within each cluster, resulting in superior network performance. Although the algorithm supports different CH patterns, the strategic placement of sensor nodes within the clustering structure is crucial for efficient data collection, aggregation, and transmission, as well as complete coverage of the sensing zones. This comprehensive coverage helps mitigate common challenges such as the hotspot problem and pothole problem. The omnidirectional communication capability of the CHs ensures maximum coverage both within and slightly beyond their designated zones.

Cluster-head selection is based on node priority, which is derived from each sensor's cumulative value. This value is compared against a predefined threshold, and nodes meeting this criterion are assigned higher priority and elected as effective CHs. In the third phase of the SwarmHex-BCCLR algorithm, path establishment is performed using the Linear Pattern Routing (LPR) mechanism. LPR facilitates data transmission by selecting sensor nodes and CHs along a predefined linear path between the source and the base station. The routing process supports multiple communication

flows, including sensor-to-CH, CH-to-sensor, CH-to-CH, and CH-to-base station. Based on these three phases, the SwarmHex-BCCLR algorithm was evaluated against existing standard techniques and demonstrates superior performance on average. The results indicate a 90% increase in network survival time, a 62% Data Delivery Ratio (DDR), an 87% improvement in throughput, and a 74% reduction in delay. Future extensions of this work may incorporate dynamic and heterogeneous node capabilities, as well as deployments in unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) networks.

Table 6: Comparison Of Various Bio-Inspired Algorithms

Algorithm	Description	Nature	Objectives / Strategies
ACO(Ant-Colony optimization)	This algorithm is developed for team based association to find effective solution	Bio-inspired	CH selection, Path decision, clustering
PSO (Particle-swarm optimization)	Algorithm developed for efficient clustering and routing process	Bio-inspired	CH selection, Collaboration, exploration, Data delivery, clustering
Whale-optimization algorithm(WAO)	This algorithm developed for optimization based clustering, involves in effective coverage	Bio-inspired	Optimization of Routing and Clustering
ABC(Artificial-Bee colony)algorithm	This algorithm developed on the basis of foraging behaviour and effective cluster formation.	Bio-inspired	Clustering, collaboration, routing
Grey-wolf optimization (GWO)	This algorithm developed based on the Grey-wolf social behaviour	Bio-inspired	Clustering, optimization, QoS, distance, delay
Spotted hyena optimization) – (SHO)	This algorithm developed based on hunting behaviour	Bio-inspired	Optimization, energy efficient
FSO& FFOA(Glow worm swarm optimization – Fruit fly optimization)	This algorithm focuses on foraging behaviour of glow worm and fruit fly.	Bio-inspired	CH selection, energy, delay, QoS parameters
ISFO(Improved sunflower optimization algorithm)	Based on the sunlight the sunflower rotation to an angle to harvest power.	Bio-inspired	Decrease in the energy usage and improve in the lifetime of WSN.
Oppositional Artificial fish swarm-moth flame optimization	Based on the foraging behaviour of the fish, optimization of clustering & routing in WSN	Bio-inspired	Increase the survival time of WSN, routing process is optimized
Multi-objective Gray-wolf-Optimization	Algorithm developed for optimization of the entire WSN	Bio-inspired	Helps to increase the lifetime by preventing premature death of sensor node
Particle distance update sea-lion optimization	This algorithm developed based on the nature behaviour of sea-lion foraging behaviour	Bio-inspired	Efficient clustering and CH selection with minimum routing
Taylor-spotted-hyena optimization	This algorithm developed basis on the foraging behaviour of spotted hyena	Bio-inspired	Effective routing with fault tolerance and improvement in efficient CH selection with reliability
Adaptive sail-fish optimization and cross layer based routing protocol	This algorithm was developed basis on the nature behaviour of sail-fish	Bio-inspired	CH selection in WSN is optimized and longevity of network survival time with low latency

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1]. C. Jiang, D. Yuan, and Y. Zhao, “Towards clustering algorithms in wireless sensor networks—A survey,” in Proc. IEEE Wireless Commun. Netw. Conf., Budapest, Hungary, Apr. 2009, pp. 1–6.
- [2]. K. Mehta and R. Pal, “Energy efficient routing protocols for wireless sensor networks: A survey,” Int. J. Comput. Appl., vol. 165, no. 3, pp. 41–46, May 2017.

- [3]. K. Mehta and R. Pal, "Biogeography based optimization protocol for energy efficient evolutionary algorithm: (BBO: EEEA)," in Proc. Int. Conf. Comput. Commun. Technol. for Smart Nation (IC3TSN), Oct. 2017, pp. 281–286.
- [4]. R. Pal and A. K. Sharma, "FSEP-E: Enhanced stable election protocol based on fuzzy logic for cluster head selection in WSNs," in P
- [5]. W. B. Heinzelman, A. P. Chandrakasan, and H. Balakrishnan, "An application-specific protocol architecture for wireless microsensor networks," IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun., vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 660–670, Oct. 2002.
- [6]. S.K. Gupta, S. Singh, Survey on energy efficient dynamic sink optimum routing for wireless sensor network and communication technologies, Int. J. Commun. Syst. vol. 35 (11) (May 2022), <https://doi.org/10.1002/dac.5194>.
- [7]. A. Ali, Y. Ming, T. Si, S. Iram, and S. Chakraborty, "Enhancement of RWSN lifetime via firework clustering algorithm validated by ANN," Information, vol. 9, no. 3, p. 60, Mar. 2018.
- [8]. J. John, P. Rodrigues, A survey of energy-aware cluster head selection techniques in wireless sensor network, Evolut. Intell. vol. 15 (2) (Nov. 2019) 1109–1121, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12065-019-00308-4>.
- [9]. Arghavani M, Esmaeili M, Mohseni F, Arghavani A(2017) Optimal energy aware clustering in circular wireless sensor networks. Ad Hoc Network 65:91-98
- [10]. X. S. Yang, Engineering Optimization: An Introduction With Metaheuristic Applications. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2010.
- [11]. X. Yang and A. H. Gandomi, "Bat algorithm: A novel approach for global engineering optimization," Eng. Computations, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 464–483, Jul. 2012.
- [12]. M. Mohammadi and N. Ghadimi, "Optimal location and optimized parameters for robust power system stabilizer using honeybee mating optimization," Complexity, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 242–258, Sep. 2015.
- [13]. M. Gamal, N.E. Mekky, H.H. Soliman, N.A. Hikal, Enhancing the lifetime of wireless sensor networks using fuzzy logic LEACH technique-based particle swarm optimization, IEEE Access vol. 10 (2022) 36935–36948, <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2022.3163254>.
- [14]. I. Surenter, K.P. Sridhar, M.K. Roberts, Enhancing data transmission efficiency in wireless sensor networks through machine learning-enabled energy optimization: a grouping model approach Ain Shams Eng. J. vol. 15 (4) (Apr. 2024) 102644, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2024.102644>.
- [15]. D.-W. Huang, F. Luo, J. Bi, M. Sun, An efficient hybrid IDS deployment architecture for multi-hop clustered wireless sensor networks, IEEE Trans. Inf. Forensics Secur. vol. 17 (2022) 2688–2702, <http://doi.org/10.1109/tifs.2022.3191491>.
- [16]. H. Ali, U.U. Tariq, M. Hussain, L. Lu, J. Panneerselvam, X. Zhai, ARSH-FATI: a novel metaheuristic for cluster head selection in wireless sensor networks, IEEE Syst. J. vol. 15 (2) (Jun. 2021) 2386–2397, <https://doi.org/10.1109/jsyst.2020.2986811>.
- [17]. T. Kaur, D. Kumar, MACO-QCR: Multi-Objective ACO-Based QoS-Aware CrossLayer Routing Protocols in WSN, IEEE Sens. J. vol. 21 (5) (Mar. 2021) 6775–6783, <https://doi.org/10.1109/jсен.2020.3038241>.
- [18]. P.P.I. Vazhuthi, A. Prasanth, S.P. Manikandan, K.K.D. Sowndarya, A hybrid ANFIS reptile optimization algorithm for energy-efficient inter-cluster routing in internet of things-enabled wireless sensor networks, Peer-to-Peer Netw. Appl. vol. 16 (2) (Mar. 2023) 1049–1068.
- [19]. V.-T. Pham, T.N. Nguyen, B.-H. Liu, M.T. Thai, B. Dumba, T. Lin, Minimizing latency for data aggregation in wireless sensor networks: an algorithm approach, ACM Trans. Sens. Netw. vol. 18 (3) (Aug. 2022) 1–21, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3450350>.
- [20]. M.K. Roberts, J. Thangavel, An optimized ticket manager-based energy-aware multipath routing protocol design for IoT based wireless sensor networks, Concurr. Comput.: Pract. Exp. vol. 34 (28) (Oct. 2022), <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.7398>.
- [21]. J.-S. Leu, T.-H. Chiang, M.-C. Yu, and K.-W. Su, "Energy efficient clustering scheme for prolonging the lifetime of wireless sensor network with isolated nodes," IEEE Commun. Lett., vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 259–262, Feb. 2015.
- [22]. J. RejinaParvin and C. Vasanthanayaki, "Particle swarm optimizationbased clustering by preventing residual nodes in wireless sensor networks," IEEE Sensors J., vol. 15, no. 8, pp. 4264–4274, Aug. 2015.
- [23]. T. Senthil Murugan and A. Sarkar, "Optimal cluster head selection by hybridisation of

- firefly and grey wolf optimisation,” *Int. J. Wireless Mobile Comput.*, vol. 14, no. 3, p. 296, 2018.
- [24]. Lata, S. Mehruz, S. Urooj, and F. Alrowais, “Fuzzy clustering algorithm for enhancing reliability and network lifetime of wireless sensor networks,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 66013–66024, 2020.
- [25]. M.S. Chen, K.G. Shin, D.D. Kandlur, Addressing, routing, and broadcasting in hexagonal mesh multiprocessors, *IEEE Transactions on Computers* 39 (1990) 10–18.
- [26]. F.G. Nocetti, I. Stojmenovic, J. Zhang, Addressing and routing in hexagonal networks with applications for tracking mobile users and connection rerouting in cellular networks, *IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems* 13 (2002) 963–971.
- [27]. Bekal, P., Kumar, P., & Mane, P. R. (2024). A metaheuristic approach for hierarchical wireless sensor networks using particle swarm optimisation-based Enhanced LEACH protocol. *IET Wireless Sensor Systems*, 14(6), 410-426. DOI:10.1049/wss2.12091.
- [28]. Cheng, Xuezhen; Xu, Chuannuo; Liu, Xiaoqing; Li, Jiming; Zhang, Junming. (2022). LEACH Protocol Optimization Based on Weighting Strategy and the Improved Ant Colony Algorithm. *Frontiers in Neurobotics*, 16:840332. DOI:10.3389/fnbot.2022.840332.
- [29]. Bhola, J., Soni, S., & Cheema, G. K. (2024). Genetic algorithm based optimized LEACH protocol for energy efficient wireless sensor networks. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, 11(3), 1281–1288
- [30]. Dhankhar, Poonam; Siwach, Vikas; Sehrawat, Harkesh. (2024). Energy Efficient Clustered Load Balanced LEACH Protocol Based on Particle Swarm Optimization in Underwater Wireless Sensor Networks. *International Journal of Communication Networks and Information Security (IJCNIS)*, 16(1), 130-145.